

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D13.2 — Data mobilisation summary

WP13 – Extension of COVID-19 Data Portal
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Contractual delivery date: **31 January 2022**
Actual delivery date: **20 September 2022**
H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2

Grant agreement no. 824087
Horizon 2020
Type of action: RIA

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of Work Package 13 is to deliver essential open data infrastructure to support urgent scientific research in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. Including both the extension of existing infrastructure through software development and the operationalisation of this extended infrastructure through deep support services, the aim is to enable and empower a substantial research effort across European and global research communities. More specifically the objectives of WP13 are to:

- 1) Mobilise open biomolecular data relevant to COVID-19 research from structured bioinformatics databases and prioritised life science RI resources via the COVID-19 Data Portal¹
- 2) Mobilise new SARS-CoV-2 biomolecular data emerging from research laboratories, national public health organisations, EU and global initiatives through the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs to the COVID-19 Data Portal
- 3) Connect biomolecular data to sensitive contextual clinical and epidemiological data that lie within dispersed controlled access repositories, presenting these through the COVID-19 Data Portal

Progress on objectives: 1 and 2 progressed well as reported in D13.1 report. Objective 3 is still underway as we move forward, as data protection-related issues have presented several challenges.

- Objective 1: Over 7.5 million records from across EMBL-EBI resources are displayed on the Portal (January 2022), with many options for search and retrieval.
- Objective 2: Also displayed on the portal are consensus sequence data from 101 countries, and raw sequencing read data coming in from 79 countries². All public raw sequencing read data are analysed with custom workflows through the data hubs system and the results also presented on the Portal.
- Objective 3: A preliminary cohort browser application (developed under ReCoDID) has been adapted and made available for the purposes of the European COVID-19 Data Platform to allow browsing linked biomolecular and clin-epi data. While the legal framework for harmonisation and linking of sensitive data continues to be developed, with a corresponding lack of data to show, this functionality is held ready for deployment in the COVID-19 Data Portal. Currently the Portal displays, via the Pathogens Portal one cohort study³.

¹ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

² <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/statistics>

³ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/cohorts>

Project Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the following objectives under Work Package 13:

- a. Mobilise open biomolecular data relevant to COVID-19 research from structured bioinformatics databases and prioritised life science RI resources via the COVID-19 Data Portal
- b. Mobilise new SARS-CoV-2 biomolecular data emerging from research laboratories, national public health organisations, EU and global initiatives through the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs to the COVID-19 Data Portal
- c. Connect biomolecular data to sensitive contextual clinical and epidemiological data that lie within dispersed controlled access repositories, presenting these through the COVID-19 Data Portal

All of the work undertaken in this deliverable is contributing to all three EOSC-Life's main objectives, namely:

- Objective 1: Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources for cloud use
- Objective 2: Create an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC
- Objective 3: Enable ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Integration of data via a COVID-19 Data Portal

This report provides a summary of data mobilisation efforts within work package 13, split by task. Firstly, task 1 included populating the COVID-19 Data Portal, the interface that integrates relevant biomolecular data and literature. At the time of reporting (August 2022), the following major progress has been made:

- Over 15 million records indexed and presenting in the portal.
- Support for cross-referencing between resources, including presentation, creating a rich, navigable network of information.
- Fast turnover - when data goes public in its relevant database, it is indexed and displaced on the portal rapidly through daily indexing schemes.
- Support for SARS-CoV-2 infectious disease cohort study datasets.
- Support for datasets which are linked across different data types, for example serological and genomic data.
- Addition of Imaging data, indexed and available through EBI Search (described below).

Data is sourced dynamically from EMBL-EBI's 54+ specialist databases, of which 21 currently provide data to the Portal, that span the EC's recommended deposition databases for COVID-19 and secondary databases deriving content from the deposition databases. This is achieved

through EMBL-EBI's centralised indexing service - EBI Search - and provides endpoints to query metadata from all EMBL-EBI services, with many resources creating COVID-19-specific services. The API endpoint documentation, provides an indication of the various specialist databases sourcing their data⁴. The indexes are updated nightly. Software developed under EOSC-Life serves to capture, structure and lay out indexed data from EBI Search in the Portal. COVID-19 data are already richly represented and are rapidly growing across EMBL-EBI data resources such as ENA, UniProt, PDBe, EMDB, Expression Atlas and EuropePMC covering genes, proteins, structures, electron microscopy data and scientific publications relating to COVID-19.

Under the infrastructure provided by EOSC-Life, the Portal will be continually enriched as new data emerge from data submissions into EMBL-EBI deposition databases and furnished with web and programmatic interfaces appropriate to support diverse and extensive research upon the data served. The COVID-19 Data Portal displays the following useful features to users:

- Improved search queries - search box can support complex queries in Apache Lucene syntax (mirroring EBI Search)⁵. Coupling this with EBI Search advanced search⁶, users are able to construct SQL-like queries which can be input in the search box.
- API to query any/all metadata held in the Portal⁷.
- Bulk downloader tool to retrieve sequencing data in various formats⁸.

2. Mobilise sequence data through the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs

The SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs have been leveraged to support the mobilisation of sequence data into the COVID-19 Data Portal. The Data Hubs support and serve data generating and brokering research laboratories, national public health organisations and international bodies by providing submission services, programmatic endpoints for integration with laboratory information management systems and tools for analysis and interpretation. They also serve as a result of these functions - for the use of EOSC-Life and the operation of the COVID-19 Data Portal - an integrated and synchronised comprehensive SARS-COV-2 sequence, assembly, variation and metadata data set.

Under EOSC-Life, we have built, maintained, extended and operated the flow of the comprehensive SARS-CoV-2 data into the COVID-19 Data Portal, providing search, browsing and various programmatic interfaces for discovery and access. With continued rapid growth of both raw and assembled sequence data coming through the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs route, at the time of writing, the COVID-19 Data Portals shows raw data from some 5.6 million SARS-CoV-2 isolates, 6 million assembled viral sequences, 2.6 million systematically-derived variation and consensus sequence sets and 73,000 variations.

Work under EOSC-Life also includes the integration and operation of a variety of tools that support a variety of user analysis and visualisation functions, such as the "CoVEO " application for viral variation investigation and the phylogeny tools.

⁴ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/api-documentation>

⁵ https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/documentation.ebi#query_syntax

⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/advanced-search.ebi>

⁷ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/api-documentation>

⁸ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/bulk-downloads>

3. Connect Life Science RI data sets to COVID-19 Data Portal

The Life Science RI facilities and repositories are accumulating COVID-19 datasets from the support to European COVID-19 research projects and data cataloguing efforts. Biomolecular data from the RI repositories and data management solutions are interfaced, via the major biomolecular archives into the COVID-19 Data Portal.

The focus in this first phase was on data types that were already partly integrated into the COVID-19 Portal - thereby closing the loop between RI data management practice and the provision of integrated COVID-19 data to the research community.

The following resources were interfaced, also covered under 13.1:

- BioImage Archive, allowing data routed from IDR and Omero to be available through the Portal.
- BBMRI-ERIC: BBMRI Catalogue (Human samples/European biobank data) improving the connectivity between BBMRI Catalogue and Biosamples for the COVID-19 Data Portal.
- CSIC: PDB+EMDB (Structural Biology data/Structure based drug design data). 3DBionotes and PDBe Knowledge Base to improve the workflow for cryo-EM data annotations and cryoEM maps and deposit these in the cryo-EM archive for publication via the COVID-19 Data Portal.
- Fraunhofer: ChEMBL, allowing data (small molecule screening/drug repurposing data to be routed from EUOSECDB to be published via the Portal.

In addition, during the reporting period for Deliverable 13.2, the Content Management System and the Portal were continually updated and improved as follows:

- Review and improvement of Partners pages
- Illumina pipeline using ftp endpoints
- Reviewed and published improvements to the search query documentation
- Addition of Samples tab
- Refactoring of the partners pages
- Improvements in the query examples
- Added additional format for download end-points
- Improved API documentation
- Launched User Survey to improve user experience
- The CoVEO app was integrated (please cf. with above)
- New section for Database resources for ease of access to the indexed Databases
- There were performance improvements for downloads
- An ArrayExpress view was added
- Various technical improvements and bug fixes to the Portal as part of ongoing support
- The top menu was improved and the Cohorts tab (please cf with 4 below) was added

4. Connect biomolecular data to external clinical/epidemiological data sets

The SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs enable high connectivity between locally held data (sequences and essential nonsensitive metadata) and deeper clinical and epidemiological data, such as

classification of symptoms, time since infection, comorbidities, treatment history and travel/contact history.

The **Cohort Browser**⁹ which was introduced as part of the RECODID project will become an integral part of COVID-19 Data Portal and primary entry point into cohort data. It lists discovery metadata of COVID-19-related cohort studies and indicates which data types are available. Where possible, basic aggregate data are also included. Search and filtering functionality will allow the users to locate datasets of interest. An early version of the cohort browser is available on EBI's ENA webpage (see footnote). A framework and a roadmap has been put in place by partners within the ReCoDID project with GDPR expertise and more data will be added to the cohort browser in the near future.

References

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- Peter W Harrison, Rodrigo Lopez, Nadim Rahman, Stefan Gutnick Allen, Raheela Aslam, Nicola Buso, Carla Cummins et al., *The COVID-19 Data Portal: accelerating SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 research through rapid open access data sharing*, Nucleic Acids Research, Volume 49, Issue W1, 2 July 2021, Pages W619–W623, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab417>

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery was delayed due to legal problems to access the necessary data, also causing a delay to two milestones (MS42 and MS43).

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/pathogens/v2/cohorts>

